

P = NP

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Abstract

P=NP

$P = NP$ because 2-SAT can be solved in P using Tarjan's algorithm, and SAT can be reduced to 2-SAT as follows.

The code shown below is entirely his [2]. The only thing is that for some reason he did not realize that he had proved $P = NP$.

```
1 def sat_to_2sat(n, clauses):
2     fresh = n + 1
3     nclauses = []
4     for clause in clauses:
5         if len(clause) == 2:
6             nclauses.append(clause)
7             continue
8         v = fresh
9         fresh += 1
10        for lit in clause:
11            nclauses.append((-lit, -v))
12        for _ in range(n):
13            nclauses.append((v, -fresh))
14            fresh += 1
15    return fresh - 1, nclauses
```

The reduction is polynomial [1]. Therefore, $P = NP$.

References

- [1] Tuomas Laakkonen, Konstantinos Meichanetzidis, and John van de Weering, *Picturing Counting Reductions with the ZH-Calculus*, Electronic Proceedings in Theoretical Computer Science, Vol. 384, 2023, pp. 89–113. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4204/EPTCS.384.6>
- [2] Tuomas Laakkonen, *Reducing #SAT to #MONOTONE-2SAT*, Theoretical Computer Science Stack Exchange, 2023. Disponible en: <https://cstheory.stackexchange.com/q/52727> Source code visible at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260315200835/https://cstheory.stackexchange.com/posts/52727/edit>